

Opinion of the Scientific Committee of the Spanish Agency for Food Safety and Nutrition (AESAN) relative to the proposal of the European Commission (EC) on nutrition claims regarding monounsaturated fatty acids (MUFA) in foods and considerations on the same proposal contributed by the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA).

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Abstract

In the context of the Proposal of Regulation concerning the use of nutrition and health claims in the labelling, presentation and advertising of foods, the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) has issued a Scientific Opinion on possible nutrition claims related to omega-3 fatty acids, monounsaturated fat, unsaturated fat and polyunsaturated fat. This Opinion is an initial response to a question raised by the European Commission in the following terms: *“The European Commission requests the EFSA to issue an opinion on the scientific substantiation of the nutrition claims relating to omega-3 fatty acids, monounsaturated fat, polyunsaturated fat and unsaturated fat.”*

In this context the Authority is asked to review the scientific merits of the following proposed claims and advise on their addition to the Annex of the proposed Regulation: *High monounsaturated fat: A claim that a food is high in monounsaturated fat, and any claim likely to have the same meaning for the consumer, may only be made where at least 45% of the fatty acids present in the product derive from monounsaturated fat under the condition that saturated fat must not provide more than 10% of energy”.*

The criteria proposed by the European Commission for monounsaturated fat claim (SFA<10%) is contradictory to the recommendation expressed by their own EFSA Scientific Panel in its report, in the same way that it contradicts what has been

endorsed by several national and international organizations. The Scientific Panel of EFSA considers to be an anomaly the fact that, while olive oil is a good monounsaturated fatty acids source, it cannot qualify for the “high monounsaturated fat” claim, when failing to fulfil the additional condition of which the saturated fatty acids content in the product must be less than 10% of the energy.

After considering scientific aspects of greatest interest related to the matter, the Scientific Committee of the AESAN concludes that the criteria proposed by the European Commission erroneously considers olive oil to be excluded from the possibility of showing the claim “high monounsaturated fat” based just on the condition that saturated fat must not provide more than 10% of energy. Numerous independent scientific opinions, including that of EFSA, demonstrate that beneficial effects have been observed when increasing the relationship between the content of monounsaturated fatty acids and saturated fatty acids, a circumstance that occurs in olive oil (main monounsaturated fatty acids source of the Mediterranean diet), a product whose consumption is recommended at an international level.

Key Words

Mono-unsaturated fatty acids (MUFA), saturated fatty acids (SFA), poly-unsaturated fatty acids (PUFA), unsaturated fatty acids (UFA), nutrition claims, olive oil, oleic acid.

1. Background

In the context of the Proposal of Regulation on the use of nutrition and health claims in the labelling, presentation and advertising of foods (EC, 2003), the EFSA, through their Scientific Panel of Dietetic Products, Nutrition and Allergies (Scientific Panel NDA) has expressed an opinion on possible nutrition claims concerning omega-3 fatty acids, monounsaturated fat, unsaturated fat and polyunsaturated fat (EFSA, 2005). This Opinion constituted a first answer of EFSA to a question on nutrition claims, that was raised by the European Commission (EC) in the following terms: *“the EC requests the EFSA to issue an opinion on the scientific substantiation of the nutrition claims relating to omega-3 fatty acids, monounsaturated fat, polyunsaturated fat and unsaturated fat. In this context the Authority is asked to review the scientific merits of the following proposed claims and advise on their addition to the Annex of the proposed Regulation: High monounsaturated fat: A claim that a food is high in monounsaturated fat, and any claim likely to have the same meaning for the consumer, may only be made where at least 45% of the fatty acids present in the product derive from monounsaturated fat under the condition that saturated fat must not provide more than 10% of energy”*

The question raised to EFSA by the EC and the referred opinion of the Scientific Panel NDA also talks about claims regarding omega-3 fatty acids, already considered by this Scientific Committee (AESAN, 2005), and polyunsaturated fat, and unsaturated fat, that are not object of consideration in the present opinion of the Scientific Committee of AESAN.

2. Considerations of the EC on the proposal of criteria concerning high monounsaturated fat claim

The criteria proposed by the EC for the high monounsaturated fat claim (SFA<10%) is contradictory to the recommendation expressed by their own Scientific Panel of EFSA in its report (EFSA, 2005), in the same way that it contradicts what has

been endorsed by several national and international organizations (WHO, 2003) (D-A-CH, 2000) (NNR, 2004) (FNB, 2002).

According to the report of EFSA, one of the main sources of MUFA is plant oils, specially olive oil and rapeseed oil. The data contributed by the report TRANSFAIR (Hulshof et al., 1999) indicate that the olive oil is the main source of MUFA in southern European countries, being 60% of the contribution of MUFA in Spain and Italy. In other EU countries, the main sources of MUFA would be meat and meat products with contributions that vary between 30% in Holland and 43% in Germany (Hulshof et al., 1999).

It is worth emphasizing that, in the analysis of the proposal of the claim that we are considering, the Scientific Panel of EFSA already considers an anomaly the fact that, while olive oil is a good source of MUFA, it cannot be included in "high in monounsaturated fat" food group, when failing to fulfil the additional condition that the content of SFA in the product must be less than 10% of the energy. In order to reach this conclusion (EFSA, 2005), the Scientific Panel takes as an example the Swedish database of food consumption that establishes a contribution of SFA for olive oil of 14% of the energy (EFSA, 2005).

The report issued by EFSA stated that MUFA, whose more important representative in the diet is oleic acid and whose main natural source is olive oil, can be synthesized in humans, and this is the reason why MUFA are not considered, formally, as essential nutrients, although the beneficial effects on health of MUFA stand out (in particular, the substitution of saturated fatty acids (SFA) by similar amounts of MUFA) in the light of numerous clinical and epidemiological studies (EFSA, 2005).

The recommendations established by several national and international organizations regarding adult population intake fix the daily fatty acids intake as a proportion of the total daily intake of energy (% E) with a SFA intake that must be equal or less than 10% of total daily intake of energy (Hulshof et al., 1999. TRANSFAIR), (D-A-CH, 2000) (NNR, 2004) (FNB, 2002) (ANC, 2001) (WHO, 2003). As a result, the recommendation is that levels of MUFA intake must be between 9% and 18% of the total energy, which corresponds approximately to 30- 50% of fatty acids for a diet in which the fat contributes 35% of energy (EFSA, 2005).

FAO and the WHO in their report on diet, nutrition and prevention of chronic diseases (WHO, 2003) recommend a fat consumption that contributes between 15% and 30% of total the daily intake of energy indicating that the SFA consumption must be equal to or less than 10% of total intake. Under the same considerations, the *American Heart Association* (Alice et al., 2006) recommends, through its committee of nutrition, intake levels of SFA in the diet less than 7%.

The common denominator is, in all cases, the recommendation is that SFA levels, that must be equal or less than 10% of the total intake of energy of the diet and the Scientific Panel of the EFSA makes reference to this recommendation in its report (EFSA, 2005).

The discrepancy arises when the limitation it is established for a high content in saturated fatty acids (SFA) in a determined food without considering the relative contribution that MUFA represents. At this point, the Proposal of the Commission does not follow the recommendation on the levels of SFA with respect to the total energy of the diet, but adopts the disqualifying threshold % of energy contributed by SFA in the

product (that does not have to be more than 10%). This criteria would cause (when considering a content of SFA in olive oil of 14% of energy) the exclusion of olive oil from this claim.

It is also highly contradictory that the intake of an amount of a product, for example 30 ml of olive oil, can contribute with the maximum daily recommendation of MUFA without contributing more than 2% of the energy intake from saturated fatty acids and that, paradoxically, is excluded from the food group that can claim to be a source of MUFA.

The contradiction also arises because the criteria that allows the incorporation of the claim makes reference, on one hand, to the percentage proportion of MUFA, PUFA and UFA with respect to the weight of foods, while the expression “% E” is reserved for SFA (EFSA, 2005).

Based on epidemiological data, it has been estimated that a reduction of 2% of the energy contributed by the SFA causes a diminution of the risk of suffering coronary cardiopathies by 25% (Mensink et al., 2003) (NDA, 2004). This data is authenticated by the indices of mortality derived from coronary cardiopathies:

Table 1 Indices of mortality associated with coronary cardiopathies in Europe

Country	Daily intake of MUFA ¹	Mortality index ²
Sweden	13%	301.7
Holland	13%	145
Spain	>18%	86.3

¹ With respect to total the daily intake of energy. Source: Sweden (Becker and Pearson. 2002), Holland and Spain (Mensink *et al.* 1999).

² Data per 100,000 people per annum; data of 1990, 1991 and 1992. Source: Statistisches Jahrbuch 1995.

Also, the fact that the beneficial effects on health have been demonstrated of reductions in the intake of SFA which are obtained by means of their substitution in similar amounts by MUFA, as is recognized in the report of the EFSA; in fact, it implies that these beneficial effects are obtained with a high MUFA:SFA relationship (Keys, 1986). The logical consequence it is that the nutrition claims of MUFA should consider the MUFA:SFA relationship in the same measurement to be at least as important as the isolated consideration of a threshold of SFA of 10% of energy.

Considering the qualifying conditions of the claim for foods with high content in MUFA, it is possible to establish that the MUFA:SFA relationship (45:10) should be at least 4.5. In the case of olive oil it is established, being based on diverse studies, an average MUFA:SFA relationship of 5.3 (Pinelli et al., 2002). It is possible to reach the same conclusion if the data of the Swedish base of food composition, mentioned in the report, is taken into account (75:14 = MUFA:SFA = 5.3) (EFSA, 2005). It is necessary to consider that of that 14% of SFA, approximately 3.5% is stearic acid which can be partly metabolized to oleic (EU, 2003) (CODEX, 2003).

From all the above, it can be deduced that one of the criteria on which the claim bases the classification of foods with high content of MUFA are the beneficial effects derived from an elevated consumption of MUFA, what implies an elevated MUFA:SFA relationship, it would be fair to consider olive oil within this classification since its relation MUFA:SFA of 5.3 is far beyond that which can be deduced from their own

criteria established in the claim proposal (MUFA:SFA = 4.5). However, some virgin olive oil from several varieties of olives can have a relationship MUFA:SFA less than 4.5, especially those that have a higher PUFA content.

In the same way, the *Food and Drug Administration* (FDA, 2003), based on a series of scientific evidence, has determined that the daily intake of MUFA, in olive oil way, which should be consumed to replace foods rich in SFA, with the condition that the daily ingestion of energy is not increased, must be approximately of 17.5 g of MUFA, which corresponds to about 23 grams of olive oil.

Conclusions of the Scientific Committee

When analyzing the Proposal relative to the nutrition claim “high monounsaturated fat”, of AESAN by the EC and the opinion on the matter expressed by Scientific Panel NDA of EFSA, the Scientific Committee concludes:

1. The criteria proposed by the EC is considered erroneous; it disqualifies the olive oil claims of MUFA based solely on the fact that the content of SFA in the product must be less than 10% (SFA<10%) of its energy, since the general recommendation of the benefits that result from increased the consumption of MUFA (in particular, by means of the olive oil intake) is supported by numerous independent scientific positions, including that of EFSA and are supported scientifically on the basis of studies in which the benefits have been observed when increasing the relationship MUFA:SFA.
In addition, the referred criteria, apart from not being supported scientifically, is located in plain contradiction with the reality of the composition of olive oil, the first source of MUFA in the euro-mediterranean diet, and to exclude olive oil from this qualification would be also contradictory with the international nutritional recommendations.
2. As an alternative to the condition that excludes a product from being able to show MUFA claims because of its elevated content of SFA, the condition can be considered that it must display a content of less than SFA 10% or a relation MUFA:SFA of more than 4.5.
3. In any case, olive oil must be considered included as a mono-unsaturated fatty acids source.

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